

Scalable Dynamic Domain Decomposition of the OpenMC Random Ray Transport Solver

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804030

ABSTRACT

A dynamic domain decomposition scheme is added to the random ray solver in OpenMC, allowing for scalability on clusters and supercomputers with MPI. The new scheme utilizes a dynamic approach to load balancing, allowing for reassignment of cell ownership between subdomains so as to ensure work is spread evenly across MPI ranks. The new capabilities in OpenMC allow for far greater parallelism and allow for finer random ray mesh resolutions to be used on large and challenging problems in fission and fusion engineering. Strong scaling studies on a tokamak model and stellarator model demonstrate 37% and 67% parallel efficiency out to 40 nodes (5120 cores) on the Argonne Improv cluster. The new domain decomposition capability supports any type of geometry in OpenMC (including constructive solid geometry, unstructured mesh, and CAD geometries).

Keywords: Random Ray Method, OpenMC, Domain Decomposition, Parallel Computing, MPI

1. INTRODUCTION

The random ray method [1] of neutral particle transport is a multigroup method closely related to the Method of Characteristics (MOC) [2]. Random ray operates by following the paths of stochastically chosen rays through a simulation geometry, solving a characteristic ordinary differential equation for the angular flux as the ray traverses each cell. Geometry cells in the context of random ray and MOC are often referred to as source regions as each cell provides neutron source data based on external sources and fission and scattering rates. The random ray method has a number of positive attributes (accuracy, memory efficiency, speed, and simplicity of implementation) that combine to offer significant potential utility. A random ray method transport solver was recently added [3] to the OpenMC [4] neutral particle transport code and has been verified. While OpenMC is primarily a Monte Carlo (MC) code, the random ray solver can rapidly generate estimates of the global adjoint flux distribution (useful for generating weight window maps to perform variance reduction for subsequent MC solves) and can serve as a reduced-fidelity solver option (in cases where rapid scoping studies or parameter sweeps are too expensive to perform with MC).

However, a key challenge remains: OpenMC's random ray implementation cannot scale beyond the resources of a single computational node, with parallel capabilities currently limited to shared memory parallelism with OpenMP threading. While OpenMC can execute coarse-grained simulations for weight window generation on a single node, the largest class of simulation problems in OpenMC (for instance, fine-grained simulation of full core nuclear reactors, or weight window generation for the largest fusion systems like ITER) will be impractical to run on a single node given the large runtimes and high memory requirements. To enable random ray simulation of the largest class of models, this paper presents a new MPI distributed memory domain decomposition capability for the OpenMC random ray solver.

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There has been previous work in the field of random ray transport in developing the method to scale across multiple nodes. An important finding of early work was that domain replication for the random ray method was not feasible for larger problems due to the high cost of having to perform an MPI “All Reduce” operation of the full scalar flux vector across all MPI ranks every iteration, for reasons discussed in more detail in [5]. Thus, efforts demonstrating scalability with random ray [5, 6] and 3D MOC [7, 8] have focused on domain decomposition, where the full spatial domain of the computational simulation is broken up and distributed across many MPI ranks.

A basic domain decomposition scheme for random ray has previously been implemented in the Advanced Random Ray Code (ARRC) [5]. The present work differs in several important areas. First, ARRC was a more limited, research-oriented application with a restricted geometry treatment. OpenMC is capable of simulating much more complex models, including those with arbitrarily complex constructive solid geometry (CSG), computer-aided design (CAD) geometry, or unstructured mesh geometries, and allows for automated source region refinement – features which all complicate domain decomposition. ARRC also used a greatly simplified approach to domain decomposition and static load balancing, using a priori predictions of computational load, and the assumption of a relatively uniform cell size – assumptions which are a poor fit for most fusion neutronics simulations. This paper presents a far more capable domain decomposition scheme that can dynamically redistribute work between MPI ranks based on empirical load measurements, allowing for efficient simulation of highly complex models.

2. DYNAMIC DOMAIN DECOMPOSITION ALGORITHM

2.1. Voronoi Decomposition

The decomposition of the spatial simulation domain follows a capacity-constrained Voronoi tessellation approach, as outlined in [9]. Each MPI rank is responsible for one Voronoi region of the problem, that is made up of all points closest to its center. In our implementation, the Voronoi center positions are determined using Lloyd’s Algorithm [10], which moves the Voronoi center to the centroid of the respective region. This approach yields compact subdomains, each with approximately equal volume. The criterion that decides which MPI rank subdomain a given cell at point \mathbf{x} belongs to, checks the squared distance to a Voronoi (MPI rank) center \mathbf{c}_r and applies an additive weight w_r :

$$\min(\|\mathbf{c}_r - \mathbf{x}\|^2 - w_r) \quad \forall \quad r \in \{1, \dots, N_{\text{ranks}}\}. \quad (1)$$

Initially all weights are set to zero. Using squared distances and additive weights ensures that Voronoi regions retain a compact, connected shape, whereas multiplicative weights and simple Euclidean distances can result in scattered and elongated Voronoi regions, as shown in [9].

In the OpenMC random ray implementation, the algorithm is not aware of the cells in the geometry a priori. Instead, cells are discovered dynamically as rays travel through the geometry and, once discovered, they get added to a list of known source regions. Whenever a ray enters a previously unknown source region, the responsible MPI rank is determined using the formula given above. Ideally, the cell centroid would be used to assign ownership unambiguously. However, because centroids positions are not known, the ray entry point is used as the position \mathbf{x} in Eq. (1) and checked against all MPI rank centers. If a cell happens to sit on a boundary between two Voronoi regions, rays from different MPI ranks may enter it at different locations, and multiple MPI ranks may therefore claim the same cell within a given transport sweep. These conflicts are resolved after each transport sweep and ownership of contested source regions is decided based on the calculated load (see below). Once each newly discovered cell has a unique owner rank, the ownership information is shared across all MPI ranks and saved in a decomposition map. This decomposition map is used to look up the responsible MPI rank, every time a ray enters a source region that has been recorded before, thereby avoiding the need to evaluate Eq. (1) again, which can be time-intensive if many MPI ranks are present.

2.2. Ray Communication

Each MPI rank is responsible for containing the bookkeeping data (e.g. scalar flux vectors) for all cells in its spatial subdomain. When rays traversing the simulation domain exit a particular subdomain, they must be transmitted between MPI ranks so they can continue until they meet their termination criteria.

Every time an MPI rank detects that a ray is leaving its subdomain, the transport of that ray stops, and the ray attributes (angular flux values, position, direction, distance traveled, etc.) get stored in a buffer. Once each MPI rank has processed all rays in its subdomain, i.e. the rays have either terminated or been moved into the buffer, all MPI ranks send their buffered ray data in a bulk synchronous communication pattern to the MPI ranks that are responsible for the respective source regions the buffered rays have entered. After communicating the ray data, each MPI rank reinitializes the received rays with the transmitted data, and the rays continue traveling. This communication pattern continues until the entire ray population (batch) of a given iteration has terminated.

2.3. Load Balancing

To ensure high parallel efficiency, it is crucial to assign each MPI rank approximately the same amount of computational work (load), such that individual MPI ranks do not spend excessive time waiting at synchronization steps (like the communication phase described in the previous subsection), whereas others still have to perform their calculations.

In many computational fields, the amount of work that is performed is fixed on a per-cell basis. In such cases, the overall load is simply a function of how many cells are contained within a given subdomain, with each cell requiring the same set of operations to be performed. However, in random ray, the load in a given cell is much more complex to determine. When a ray crosses a cell, the characteristic equation (which involves an exponential term that must be evaluated) must be solved for each energy group. Additionally, to determine the length of the ray through the cell (and which cell comes next), ray tracing operations must be performed. How often rays cross a cell and how expensive the ray trace operations are depends on the size, aspect ratio and complexity of a given cell, which can vary strongly across the problem. Thus, the work to process a single cell each batch is determined by: 1) the number of rays that pass through it and 2) the ray tracing costs associated with the definition of that cell.

2.3.1. Load Estimation Formula

We estimate the load (computational work) associated with a given cell i using an empirical formula:

$$\text{load}_{\text{estimate},i} = F_r \cdot (C_1 \cdot n_{\text{hits},i} \cdot N_G + C_2 \cdot n_{\text{RT},i}) . \quad (2)$$

This formula is based on the number of ray crossings n_{hits} and the number of surface ray trace operations n_{RT} per cell, which are recorded throughout the simulation. They are weighted with factors C_1 and C_2 , which reflect the computational expense of these operations. The values of these factors were determined from empirical tests as $C_1 = 1.0$ and $C_2 = 0.1$. Because these factors are only based on estimates, this formula does not fully predict the true computational cost, and therefore an additional prefactor F_r is computed for each MPI rank based on the ratio between measured and estimated load in the current batch. No additional timers are needed in the code to calculate this factor because transport sweep times are recorded by default for diagnostics. The load of an MPI rank is then calculated by summing up the load estimates for each cell belonging to that MPI rank.

2.3.2. Balancing Strategy

We implemented a load balancing routine that tries to equalize the estimated load per MPI rank. To do so, the weight w_r of Eq. (1) is adjusted iteratively for each MPI rank based on the deviation of its calcu-

lated load from the target load. Changing this weight increases or decreases the reach of a specific MPI rank, and thus the number of cells that belong to it. After each weight change, the rank load estimates are updated according to the anticipated changes in the ownership of source regions, and the new load estimates are then used again to calculate new weights. These iterations continue until convergence or until a maximum number of iterations is reached. The implemented load balancing procedure applies various damping, adaptation and inertial factors to avoid oscillations across the iterations. This is only a preliminary approach, and future work will investigate more robust optimization procedures.

After the load balancing iterations have concluded, numerous source regions will belong to new MPI ranks. The corresponding cell data is transferred to the new owner ranks and erased from the previous owner ranks. Since both the iterative load optimization and source region exchange can be computationally expensive, load balancing is restricted to the first 5 simulation batches. Random ray simulations should use an appropriately large ray population such that at least 99 % of source regions are traversed per batch. It is therefore expected that load estimate data for the vast majority of cells has been recorded after 5 batches, and the load per MPI rank will not change significantly after that. This was confirmed during testing on the benchmark problems outlined below.

3. VERIFICATION

One key advantage of our domain decomposition scheme is that the original source region mesh is exactly preserved. Regardless of parallel configuration, the same rays will be sampled, and they will travel through the same set of source regions such that simulation results will be fully reproducible (within the limits of floating point non-associativity). Thus, our new solver can be easily verified by testing it against the existing solver and ensuring the same results are generated.

To this end, we utilize the 2D C5G7 benchmark problem [11], which features four simplified 2D reactor assemblies surrounded by a reflector region. Tests were performed on a node of the *Improv* cluster at Argonne National Laboratory, which features dual-socket AMD 7713 64 core CPU processors (128 cores per node, with hardware threads disabled). The simulation mesh featured 142,964 flat source regions and 7 energy groups. The simulation was run twice with the same random number seed: once with the original version of OpenMC with a single MPI rank and 128 OpenMP threads (no domain decomposition), and once with our new domain decomposition scheme on 128 MPI ranks with 1 thread per rank. Both runs produced an identical eigenvalue of 1.18626 ± 0.00038 . Pin powers were also compared against the reference multigroup Monte Carlo benchmark solution, with average absolute pin power errors of 0.5534%, and a maximum pin power error of 2.0456% in both cases. Thus, as the same results are generated as in the existing shared memory-only implementation, the new domain decomposition scheme can be considered fully verified.

4. PARALLEL SCALING RESULTS

In this section, we first test the new domain decomposition scheme in OpenMC on the UKAEA “Simple Tokamak” benchmark [12], a large fixed source fusion neutronics simulation problem. This problem is a nearly “worst case” challenge problem for domain decomposition as it features extreme spatial mesh resolution differences, with fine detail and small cells in areas like the divertor, and extremely coarse mesh resolution in void areas of the problem, as shown in Fig. 1. Furthermore, the high complexity of the wall of the fusion device results in some cells being bounded by hundreds of CSG surfaces (making for extremely high ray tracing costs), while other areas (like the shield wall) are constrained with just a few planar surfaces. The model is therefore a highly load imbalanced problem that makes it an ideal test case for our dynamic load balancing scheme. All tests are performed on the *Improv* cluster at Argonne National Laboratory (whose node architecture is described in section 3).

As a first step, we performed a study to determine the optimal configuration (in terms of how many MPI ranks to use on each node) for the solver. We found that OpenMC performed best on this node

Figure 1. The subfigures show the “Simple Tokamak” problem and results that are obtained with the random ray solver in OpenMC using the implemented domain decomposition scheme.

architecture when 8 MPI ranks (each with 16 OpenMP threads) were used on each node, which is likely due to improved efficiency gained from constraining shared memory operations to occur within Non-Uniform Memory Access (NUMA) domains of the dual-socket node. Simulating the Simple Tokamak benchmark in this configuration gave a speed-up of $77\times$ compared to running on a single thread in serial. This is lower than the ideal of a $128\times$ speed-up because some overhead is being paid for the domain decomposition features and because there is inherent contention for resources (e.g., last level cache) that are shared between cores.

To determine the scaling efficiency of our domain decomposition scheme, we performed a strong scaling study from one node out to 40 nodes (5120 cores), keeping the mesh size fixed. Studies were performed both with and without our dynamic load balancing enabled, so as to quantify the impact of this feature. Simulations for the strong scaling study were run with a total of 4 million rays per batch. Buffering ray data on interfaces between MPI rank subdomains requires 72 bytes of memory per ray, totaling 288 MB for this problem.

The results of our strong scaling analysis, shown in Fig. 2, reveal the strong scaling improvements that our dynamic load balancing approach achieves. When running on a single node (just 8 MPI subdomains), the dynamic load balancing scheme requires about 32 % less total runtime than the unbalanced version. When scaled to 40 nodes (the maximum available to a user on *Improv*), our dynamic load balancing strategy allows for significant walltime reductions and an overall speed-up of $1.81\times$ compared to the unbalanced equal-volume decomposition method. The load balancing scheme itself made up only 0.63 % of the overall runtime in this case. At 40 nodes, the load-balanced version achieves a 16 % discrepancy in transport time between the slowest MPI rank and the average, whereas the unbalanced version suffers from an imbalance of 284 %. It is likely that further runtime reductions can be achieved if scaled out to an even higher number of nodes. Overall, our decomposition scheme allowed us to perform highly detailed modeling of the tokamak model in only 10.18 minutes, whereas before 220.55 minutes were required when constrained to a single node with OpenMP threading only.

As the problem was strong scaled to higher node counts, we did observe an increasing deviation from ideal scaling behavior due to the progressive loss of parallel efficiency. At the highest case, with 40 nodes, only 37 % parallel efficiency was achieved compared to single node operation. At this scale, ray communication operations began to dominate the runtime of the code. While further improvements to parallel efficiency and scaling may be possible in the future by optimizing communication bottlenecks, our current implementation is more than sufficient to allow for simulation of the largest classes of simulation problems with reasonable walltimes.

(a) Total simulation time

(b) Transport and ray communication times (load balanced)

Figure 2. Results of the strong scaling study for the “Simple Tokamak” problem

For a second strong scaling study, we applied our domain decomposition scheme to a CAD-based geometry problem. The problem selected for this second test case is a simplified stellarator model by the company Proxima Fusion [13], depicted in Fig. 3.

Again, we performed all calculations on the *Improv* cluster both with and without dynamic load balancing enabled. The stellarator problem is made up of about 24 million source regions, an order of magnitude more than the CSG tokamak model. Due to its size, it is not possible to run this problem on a single node, but at least 4 nodes are required, which underscores the need for domain decomposition to simulate models of this scale.

Fig. 4 shows the runtime results of the strong scaling study performed on the stellarator problem. The implementation of dynamic load balancing achieves runtimes that are 13 to 27% faster than the unbalanced decomposition approach. The load balancing feature amounted to less than 3% added runtime cost at the maximum node count. Compared to the first simulation run on 4 nodes, the load balanced approach achieves 67% scaling efficiency for the maximum of 40 nodes. The parallel efficiency for the stellarator problem is higher than for the tokamak case due to two reasons: 1) Strong scaling for the stellarator starts at 4 nodes, whereas the tokamak scaling study begins on a single node. Expanding the simulation from a single node to several nodes incurs an efficiency loss because inter-node MPI communication is slower compared to communication within a single node. This efficiency loss is al-

(a) Geometry (dimensions in cm)

(b) Neutron flux (group 1)

Figure 3. The subfigures show the Proxima Fusion stellarator problem and neutron flux results that are obtained with the random ray solver in OpenMC using the implemented domain decomposition scheme.

Figure 4. Results of the strong scaling study for the Proxima Fusion stellarator problem.

ready included in the initial runtime on 4 nodes for the stellarator problem. 2) For the stellarator, less time is spent transmitting rays, making the reduction in execution time for the transport sweep more noticeable at higher node counts. The reduction in ray communication is a result of the flat shape of the stellarator problem, where each MPI rank has fewer neighbors and therefore fewer chances to “lose” rays to neighboring MPI ranks.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we introduced a domain decomposition scheme for the random ray neutron flux solver in OpenMC, which has the ability to adjust the computational load between MPI ranks dynamically based on data collected during the simulation. This load balancing scheme can dynamically redistribute cell data between MPI ranks in each batch, effectively re-drawing the lines of domain decomposition in response to observed load imbalances.

We verified our domain decomposition approach on the 2D C5G7 benchmark, confirming that both the decomposed simulation with multiple MPI ranks and the original version with a single MPI rank produce exactly the same results within the limits of floating point precision. To test the efficiency of the implemented decomposition scheme, strong scaling studies were carried out on the Argonne *Improv* cluster on two fusion engineering models: a CSG tokamak model and a CAD stellarator model, both representing large, complex simulation problems. Runtimes continued to decrease up to 40 nodes (5120 cores), the maximum number available for a single job on the cluster, yielding parallel efficiencies of 37 and 67 %, respectively. At higher node counts, efficiency losses became increasingly apparent due to the rising cost of ray communication. The dynamic load balancing approach achieved runtime reductions of 13-45 % compared to unbalanced domain decomposition.

The presented work demonstrates that the implemented domain decomposition scheme successfully handles challenging simulation problems and enables the future application of the random ray solver in OpenMC to the largest classes of simulation problems, such as high-fidelity full core nuclear reactor models and large fusion device models like ITER. Future work may focus on more advanced optimization procedures for load balancing and efficiency improvements in the communication routines.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the University of Cambridge Harding Distinguished Postgraduate Scholars Programme and the EPSRC grant MaThRad (EP/W026899/1). The material was based upon work

supported by the U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Science, under contract DE-AC02-06CH11357. We gratefully acknowledge the computing resources provided on Improv, a high-performance computing cluster operated by the Laboratory Computing Resource Center at Argonne National Laboratory.

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